

HORIZON 2020

Coordination and Support Action

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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

Deliverable No. 1.5

Policy Guidance Panel implemented incl. terms of
reference

Submission of Deliverable

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Lead Beneficiary	CNRS (partner 2)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – CNRS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3 - NERC-BAS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4 - CNR-DTA, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – IPEV, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - IGOT-UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – RUG, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – MINECO, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – CSIC, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - UW-APRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – GEUS, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – VUB, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – RBINS, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - IGF PAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 - IG-TUT, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 20 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 - GINR
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EU-PolarNet Policy Guidance Panel

In accepting membership of the EU-PolarNet Policy Guidance Panel (PPGP), the individual/organization agrees to be bound by the Terms of Reference listed in Annex 1.

Context/Background

One of the main tasks of EU-PolarNet is to implement a continuous dialogue with relevant units of the European Commission and to provide advice to them or other national policy makers on questions about Polar-related topics:

- The PPGP will support EU-PolarNet in policy-related questions asked by the European Commission or other decision makers.
- The PPGP's mission is to provide evidence-based advice to the European Commission and other decision-makers through EU-PolarNet.
- The PPGP consists of experts from the economic, scientific and societal sectors nominated by the EU-PolarNet partners. It shall react quickly on questions coming from the EC or other decision makers via the EU-PolarNet coordinator. The PPGP must ensure that the views it expresses are representative of, and the services it provides are in line with, EU-PolarNet needs.

Role and scope of the Policy Guidance Panel

- The Panel will support EU-PolarNet in its relation with the EC and policy makers.
- The Panel is established in order to provide evidence-based advice on pressing policy issues related to the Polar Regions. The Panel has the following roles:
 - to respond to requests from EU-PolarNet, and possibly through EU-PolarNet from the European Commission and other national policy makers, to issues related to the Polar Regions,
 - to consult with any actor in the Polar Regions, for the benefit of EU policy makers and their counterparties in EU-PolarNet member states.
- The Panel will fulfill this role by:
 - being constituted so as to be representative of the key sectors of the Polar Regions;
 - meeting only on request;
 - participating in the EU-PolarNet policy briefing meetings.

Officers

Chair

- Duties
 - The Chair will oversee an efficient and effective operation of the Panel in accordance with the Terms of Reference.
 - In fulfilling these duties the Chair will use best endeavors to act independently in accordance with any legal or regulatory requirements.
 - In particular, the Chair (with the assistance of the Secretary) shall ensure that the Panel conducts its work in accordance with the requirements of EU regulations.
- Appointment
 - The Chair will be elected by a simple majority vote of the Panel members and finally endorsed by the General Assembly.
 - Relevant experience/criteria include
 - Broad experience on the Polar Regions
 - Recognized authority among actors in the economic, scientific and societal business sectors of the Polar Regions

- Ability to represent actors' interests to external bodies (EU-PolarNet Executive and Advisory Boards, European Commission)
- Reputation for fairness and integrity
- Technical knowledge
- Any person appointed for membership of the Panel must be prepared to serve as Chair if selected.
- Termination
 - The term of office of the Chair is 2 years, with the possibility of re-election for one more term.
 - By notice served by the EU-PolarNet coordinator and endorsed by the General Assembly, the Chair may be removed from office if he/she
 - ceases to fulfill the requirements of membership of the Panel,
 - becomes incapable of performing the functions of the office as outlined in the Terms of Reference whether by illness, infirmity, or incompetence,
 - or is found by a properly constituted supervisory authority to have breached any law or regulation applicable to his/her professional role.

Deputy Chairs

- Duties

The Deputy Chairs shall perform the functions of the Chair in the event of the Chair's absence, incapacity or on an interim basis in the event of the Chair's removal.

- Appointment

- The Deputy Chairs will be elected by a simple majority of the appointed members of the Panel for the 2 remaining sectors (economic, scientific or societal), excluding the sector of expertise of the Chair.
- Relevant experience/criteria
 - Broad experience in one of the 3 polar sectors
 - Recognized authority among actors in one of the 3 polar sectors
 - Ability to represent Polar actors' interests to external bodies
 - Reputation for fairness and integrity
 - Technical knowledge
- Any person appointed for Membership of the Panel must be prepared to serve as Deputy Chair if appointed.

- Termination

- The term of office of a Deputy Chair is 2 years, with the possibility of re-election for one more term.
- By notice served by the EU-PolarNet coordinator and endorsed by the General Assembly, the Deputy Chair may be removed from office if he/she
 - ceases to fulfill the requirements of membership of the Panel,
 - becomes incapable of performing the functions of the office as outlined in the Terms of Reference whether by illness, infirmity, or incompetence,
 - or is found by a properly constituted supervisory authority to have breached any law or regulation applicable to his/her professional role.

Secretary

Duties

The Secretary will be responsible for the efficient administration of the Panel including the convening of meetings, preparation and circulation of minutes, reporting, timely follow-up of agreed actions; The Secretary shall ensure that members of the Panel comply with the PPGP Terms of Reference, bringing any potential breaches to the attention of the Chair and EU-PolarNet Executive Board.

The Secretary will bring to the Chair of the Panel any policy issue received by the EU-PolarNet coordinator from the EU or any European national policy maker. The Secretary will report

recommendations or conclusions issued from the Panel meeting to the EU-PolarNet coordinator for transmission.

Appointment

The Secretary will be a member of the EU-PolarNet Management Support Team.

Membership of the Panel

The Panel shall consist of 14 appointed Members, including the chairs. This membership will be reviewed in accordance with the following points:

- The EU-PolarNet Executive and Advisory Boards will review the membership and composition of the Panel prior to the appointment process in December each year to ensure it meets with the requirements of the Terms of Reference.
- Current membership: The members of the Panel are listed in Appendix 1 hereto.
- Membership criteria: Members of the Panel may be drawn from the following groups
 - Representatives of EU-PolarNet partners.
 - Representatives of different Polar economic, scientific and societal sectors.
 - Representatives of Polar organizations associated with EU-PolarNet (IASC, SCAR, Arctic Council...)
 - In the event that a Panel member no longer meets the requirements then his/her membership shall cease and the vacancy shall be filled.

Meetings

- The Chair, or in his/her absence one of the Deputy Chairs, shall preside at meetings.
- The conduct of meetings via modern support such as email exchanges or video-/teleconferencing must be strongly encouraged.
- A copy of the draft minutes of every meeting of the Panel shall be sent as soon as reasonably practicable to every member of the Panel. The minutes remain in draft until adopted by the Panel.
- The quorum for a meeting of the Panel shall be four of its members.
- The Secretary shall prepare a quarterly summary of the work of the Panel to report to EU-PolarNet Executive and Advisory Boards. This summary report must be submitted in advance of the quarterly Executive Board meetings.
- The PPGP Chairman shall report to the EU-PolarNet General Assemblies concerning activities during the past year and current activities.
- Where it is deemed necessary the Panel may set up a sub-group to deal with specific topics and invite a limited number of members and co-opted experts to participate (a "Sub-Group"). The Sub-Group shall report back to the Panel with any recommendations, which will be considered by the Panel.

Annex 1

Terms of Reference

Statement of Need

Increased awareness of the environmental changes impacting the Polar regions, the recent initiatives developed by the European Commission in refining its Arctic policy, and the rapid evolution of economic and societal changes in the Polar regions, and especially in the Arctic have driven a need for timely guidance on how new developments change practice for Polar actors.

Goal of the Guidance

The goal of the Guidance is to provide up-to-date evidence-based explicit and implementable recommendations, advice or briefings on questions related to the Polar regions from the European Commission and European national policy makers.

Panel members

14 (11 + chairs) Panel members are chosen, after nomination by EU-PolarNet partners, based on their expertise in Polar research, economic development and management, and Arctic societies. Members from various stakeholder categories are also included. Members are appointed by the EU-PolarNet General Assembly after vetting by the EU-PolarNet Executive and Advisory Boards. All Panel chairs and members serve as volunteers (not compensated) for defined terms (2 years), which may be renewed based on Panel needs. The Panel chairs are elected by the Panel members and endorsed by EU-PolarNet General Assembly, and should be recruited from business, science and the Arctic residents (indigenous and local populations).

Conflict of interest management

The Panel is established with the aim of avoiding all potential professional and financial conflicts of interest among its chairs and its Panel members. All potential Panel members are asked to disclose any potential financial or scientific/professional conflicts of interest. Disclosures must be made prior to the Panel member appointments and covering 1 year prior to initiation of work on the Panel. Full transparency of potential financial and scientific conflicts is important to ensure the credibility of the process and the advice/recommendations.

Individuals are also asked to disclose funding of polar research activities to their institutional division, department, or working group.

Sponsors, funding, and collaborating Partner

EU-PolarNet is the sponsor of PPGP. AWI (and CNRS) as leads of Task 1.4 in WP1 (Evidence-based policy guidance) are the Collaborating Partners responsible for managing the Panel and the guidance development process.

Evidence identification and collection

Guidance is to be developed using an evidence-based review of information that is largely available to Polar actors. Data and information from the following sources will be considered by Panel members when making recommendations: research published in the peer-reviewed literature or presented at major national or international scientific conferences; reports or other material from the different Arctic Council working groups, Antarctic Treaty System, IASC and SCAR working groups, UN agencies or national agencies with an Arctic and/or Antarctic science program; or from relevant organizations or manufacturers including companies

developing products for Polar activities. Press releases, unpublished reports, and personal communications are generally not considered.

Literature searches will be conducted regularly and before each major policy revision to ensure that the Panel considers all relevant published data. Polar subject headings and free text terms are combined to maximize retrieval of relevant citations from Scopus, and Web of Science databases. To be considered for inclusion, articles are required to have been published in English from 2010 to the present. Data and information from abstracts presented at national or international scientific conferences will also be considered.

Rating of the evidence and recommendations

The Guidance is presented in the form of recommendations, advice or briefings. Each recommendation is rated in terms of the level of its evidence and strength. A summary of the supporting (and conflicting) evidence follows each recommendation or set of recommendations.

Data review and synthesis and preparation of recommendations and supporting information

Draft recommendations are developed by subgroups of the full Panel with interest and expertise in particular sections of the Guidance. Following development of supporting text and references, the sections are reviewed by the full Panel and Chairs. A penultimate draft is submitted to EU-PolarNet Advisory and Executive Boards for final review and approval before transmitting eventually as needed to EU-PolarNet partners, the European Commission or national policy makers.

Subgroups of the Panel meet regularly by teleconference as needed to update recommendations and supporting evidence. Updates may be prompted by new publications or presentations at major national or international scientific conferences, a new international agreement (or new indications, dosing formulations, or frequency of dosing), new Arctic Council and Antarctic Treaty decisions, or other information that may have a substantial impact on the European Polar Policy. Updates and changes in the Guidance are indicated by highlighted text on the ad-hoc online site and a notice of update is posted on the Home Page.

Opportunity for Comments

The Panel will consider evidence-based comments about the recommendations, ratings, and evidence summary but should not be contacted for individual questions. EU-PolarNet partners may submit evidence-based comments to the Panel through a dedicated EU-PolarNet intranet page within 2 weeks of the posting of the recommendation, rating or evidence summary.

Annex 2

Proposed EU-PolarNet PPGP Membership

Chair:

1. *Frej Sorento Dichmann*, Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation of the Ministry of Higher Education and Science, Denmark Deputy

Deputy Chairs:

2. *Bjorn Dahlbäck*, Director, Swedish Polar Research Secretariat, Sweden
3. *Michał Łuszczuk*, Scientific Secretary of the Committee on Polar Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland

Members:

4. *Jane Francis*, Director, British Antarctic Survey (BAS), UK
5. *Naja Mikkelsen*, Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS), IASC Vice-President, Denmark
6. *Nalan Koc*, Research Director Norwegian Polar Institute, Fram Centre, Norway
7. *Vito Vitale*, Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (ISAC), Italian National Research Council (CNR), Italy
8. *Heidi Kassens*, Director Otto Schmidt Laboratory for Polar and Marine Research (OSL) in St. Petersburg, GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research, Germany
9. *Denis-Didier Rousseau*, Scientific Director of the French Arctic Initiative, CNRS Institut National des Sciences de l'Univers, France
10. *Yves Frenot*, Director, Institut Polaire Français Paul-Emile Victor (IPEV), France
11. *Halldor Johannssen*, Executive Director Arctic Portal, Island.
12. *Gonzalo Vieira*, Associate Professor, Centro de Estudos Geográficos, Universidade de Lisboa (IGOT), Portugal
13. *Gertrude Saxinger*, Department for Social and Cultural Anthropology, University of Vienna & APRI – Austrian Polar Research Institute, Austria
14. *Christine Valentin*, World Ocean Council, France

Secretary: AWI staff